

A Simulation-Based Machine Learning Approach for Optimizing Preform Charges in Sheet Molding Compound Manufacturing

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August, 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's **Horizon Europe** Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101091449

The Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) process is widely used for producing composite structures in high-volume manufacturing due to its efficiency and scalability.

- **Challenges associated with complex mold geometries**
 - What is the initial charge shape for optimal mold filling and low material overflow ?
 - How to reduce flow bouncing on the boundary since it could perturbate fiber orientation ?
- **State of the art solution**
 - If assumed initial charge shape, simulation can predict final material distribution along with fiber orientation.
 - Requires trial and error to find the initial shape.
 - No scientific approach or adapted simulation tool.
 - **Limitation:**
 - Computationally expensive
 - Non-optimized initial charge shapes
- **Objectives:**
 - Develop a reverse flow simulation tool that can compute the initial charge shape if given final mold geometry.
 - Create a digital twin of the SMC reverse simulation that can predict initial charge shape in real-time.
 - In this research, we first limit our approach for 2D molds.

SMC simulation on a part manufactured by MARELLI as a technology demonstrator for the SMC process

SMC flow simulation:

- SMC simulation enabled by solving [1, 2]:

- Stokes equation simplified for narrow gaps by lubrication theory: $\nabla P = \eta \Delta v$

- η = dynamic viscosity,
 - P = Pressure field
 - v = velocity field

- Constant mesh grid

- We distinguish fluid domain $\Omega_f(t)$ where P is to be computed from empty domain $\Omega_e(t)$ where $P=0$

- By setting appropriate BCs, the average velocity field in 2D: $\tilde{v}(x,y) = -\frac{h^2}{3\eta} \nabla P$

- Since the fluid domain is evolving, we need to describe the fluid front by:

$$I(x, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in \Omega_f(t) \\ 0 & \text{if } x \in \Omega_e(t) \end{cases} \text{ with: } I(x, t = 0) = I_{init}$$

- $I(x, t)$ is described by: $\frac{\partial I(x,t)}{\partial t} + v(x, t) \cdot \nabla I(x, t) = 0$

- Combining the equations of P and I leads to the weak-formulation:

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(I \nabla \hat{P} \left(\frac{h^2}{3\eta} \nabla P \right) + (1 - I) \hat{P} P \right) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} (I \hat{P} \tilde{U}) d\Omega$$

References:

- [1] J. García, L. Gascón and F. Chinesta. A fixed mesh numerical method for modelling the flow in liquid composites moulding processes using a volume of fluid technique. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 192(7–8): 877–893, 2003.
- [2] F. Ebrahimian, S. Rodriguez, D. Di Lorenzo and F. Chinesta, Optimization of precharge placement in sheet molding compound process. *International Journal of Material Forming*. Vol. 17, 2024.

SMC flow simulation:

- Solving eq.(1) and eq.(2) numerically includes using flux limiters for I :

$$\frac{\partial I(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \nabla I(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(I \nabla \hat{P} \left(\frac{h^2}{3\eta} \nabla P \right) + (1 - I) \hat{P} P \right) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} (I \hat{P} \tilde{U}) d\Omega$$

- For cell e , field values at time step t_{i+1} are deduced from time step t_i :

$$I_{i+1}^e = I_i^e - \frac{\Delta t}{A(e)} \sum_{j=1}^3 l^{ej} \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ej} \cdot \mathbf{n}^{ej} \rightarrow \Phi = \text{flow flux}$$

$$h(t_{i+1}) = h_0 - \frac{U * t_{i+1}}{2}$$

Reverse SMC flow

$$I_{i+1}^e = I_i^e + \frac{\Delta t}{A(e)} \sum_{j=1}^3 l^{ej} \hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ej} \cdot \mathbf{n}^{ej}$$

$$h(t_{i+1}) = h_0 + \frac{U * t_{i+1}}{2}$$

- With:

- $A(e)$ is the area of the control volume
- \mathbf{n}^{ej} is the outward unit vector on the common edge of control volumes e and j
- l^{ej} is the length of that edge
- $\hat{\mathbf{f}}^{ej} \cdot \mathbf{n}^{ej}$ represents the fluid flux across this edge.

Simulation conditions

- 1000 simulation performed for diverse 2D mold shapes
- Reverse flow simulation starting with a charge thickness of 5mm.
 - Define fluid domain using control points forming a closed curve
 - Use NURBS to avoid sharp corners

- Mold velocity 1 mm/s for 36s with 12 000 time steps.
- Computational cost: ~12 min on a: 13th Gen Intel Core i9-13950HX CPU clocked at 2.20 GHz and equipped with 32GB of memory.

Simulation applications and results

Simulation applications and results

Simulation applications and results

Pushing the method to the extreme

Basic conclusions

- Reverse simulation is a powerful tool to predict initial charge shape for the SMC process
- Computational cost is low when considering 2D flow over a flat 2D mold.
- Computational cost could scale if mold is 3D
- When performing reverse SMC simulation to compute initial charge shapes and then based on the computed initial shape perform a standard SMC simulation, we notice that some elements are lost (mass is not fully conserved).
- Simulation is dependent on mesh size, time steps and other numerical parameters: need to fine tune such parameters for optimized outcome

Motivation for a machine learning based digital twin

- Machine learning :
 - could provide equivalent accuracy with faster computational cost
 - could work in real-time on SMC machines
 - is independent of mesh size and numerical parameters
- Machine learning is to be evaluated as a tool for creating digital twin when SMC simulation is extended to include
 - 3D applications including
 - fiber orientation

} Increased computational cost

Requirements

- Inputs and outputs are both images and can't be dealt with differently.
- Grey image only considered with 1 indicating SMC material and 0 indicating no material.
- Other important inputs are:
 - charge initial thickness
 - charge final thickness.Initial and final thicknesses are different from one use case to the other
- SMC process simulation is not history dependent. GRU, LSTM and similar RNNs are not necessary.

Options

- Convolutional Neural Network should be used to deal with images
- Combining image input with initial and desired thicknesses of charges require an embedding layer
- Possible architectures include :
 - Convolutional Autoencoders
 - GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks) or more specifically Conditional GANs (cGAN)
 - Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) or U-Net Autoencoder
- Best match is a U-Net Autoencoder with skip connections between corresponding layers of the encoder and decoder. This helps propagate fine details from the higher-resolution layers in the encoder directly to the decoder, avoiding loss of spatial information

Block ID	Block Nature	Input Channels	Output Channels	Other Characteristics
CB1	Convolutional Block	1	32	-
MP1	Max Pooling	-	-	max pooling = 2
CB2	Convolutional Block	32	64	-
MP2	Max Pooling	-	-	max pooling = 2
LS	Latent Space Block	64	128	-
TS1	Transpose convolutional layer	128	64	drop out = 30 %
SC	Skip connection	-	-	-
CB3	Convolutional Block	128	64	-
TS2	Transpose convolutional layer	64	32	drop out = 30 %
SC	Skip connection	-	-	-
CB4	Convolutional Block	64	32	-
CL	Convolutional layer	32	1	kernel size = 3, padding = 1
LL	Logical Activation Layer	-	-	-

Details of a convolutional block

ID	Layer Nature	Input Channels	Output Channels	Kernel Size	Padding	Dropout Rate
1	Convolutional layer	x_{in}	x_{out}	3	1	-
2	ReLu activation layer	x_{out}	x_{out}	-	-	-
3	Dropout	x_{out}	x_{out}	-	-	30 %
4	Convolutional layer	x_{in}	x_{out}	3	1	-
5	ReLu activation layer	x_{out}	x_{out}	-	-	-
6	Dropout	x_{out}	x_{out}	-	-	30 %

Important features:

- 466,000 trainable parameters
- 1000 simulation cases
 - 200 kept for testing and never seen by the network during training
 - 100 used for validation during training. Help prevent overfitting
- 2000 training epochs with decreasing learning rate
- Accelerated training using GPUs

- Test on a complex mold shape
 - Available charge thickness 41 mm
 - Part thickness 5 mm

- ML solution is “filtered”:
 - Smooth charge boundary
 - No local material loss
- Predicted charge shape and thickness perfectly aligns with problem physics

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Reverse SMC simulation

ML prediction

ML vs Simulation difference

- ❑ Created a numerical simulation tool that reverses the SMC simulation process and predicts the initial charge shape
- ❑ Implemented a digital twin for 2D SMC reverse flow using a UNet Auto-Encoder architecture
 - ML prediction matches simulation precision on unseen data sets.
 - Error is around 5% on unseen data.
 - Max error on few cases could reach 15% and minimum error is lower than 1%.
- ❑ **Future Expansion:**
 - Expand to include fiber orientation.
 - Expand to 2D flow over non-flat (3D) molds.